

«НОМО VIRTUALIS» – ПРОБЛЕМА ВИРТУАЛЬНОГО ЧЕЛОВЕКА

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Аннотация.

Данная статья основана на том, что проблема «Номо Virtualis» - виртуального человека становится главной проблемой 21 века, с технической и физической точки зрения виртуальность является продуктом постиндустриальной цивилизации и информационно-электронной революции, его следует понимать, как необходимый компонент информационного общества.

Ключевые слова.

бытье, виртуальная реальность, киберугроза, технология, индивидуализация, технократическое мировоззрение.

"HOMO VIRTUALIS" - THE PROBLEM OF A VIRTUAL PERSON

Abstract.

This article is based on the fact that the problem of "Homo Virtualis" - a virtual person is becoming the main problem of the 21st century, from a technical and physical point of view, virtuality is a product of post-industrial civilization and the information-electronic revolution, it should be understood as a necessary component of the information society.

Key words.

reality, virtual reality, cyber threat, technology, individualization, technocratic worldview.

Introduction. Thinking about the phenomenon of Virtual reality, we would like to focus on the fact that it should be associated with the pursuit of a specific

goal. But aiming can be conscious and unconscious. When Virtual reality is created consciously, it acquires the attribute of an artifact—an artificially created object, losing its irrelevance.

Virtual reality is non-reality. We support B.Turaev's opinion that "In the context of alternative philosophical teachings to the global: social, economic, political, spiritual, ideological problems of the present world, the approach is a condition for determining both the reasons for their origin and the consequences, as well as the scope of the work".¹ In this sense, science and philosophy are enriched by concepts such as self-organization, design, openness, closeness, linearity, helplessness, balance - imbalance, Chaos - Order, actualization - potential, dynamics - homeostasis, stability - instability. One such fundamental innovative methodological method is virtualism. Information reality, presented in the form of the Internet and other technologies, affects a person more than events in the physical world.

Literature review. Nowadays, we cannot be mistaken to say that virtual reality has reached the peak of its popularity. The number of users of Virtual reality, the relationship between them, the peculiarities are so colorful that it has become a necessity to study them philosophically. The core of the newest vision in understanding the essence of Virtual existence is the social creativity of a person. In this, virtual existence is understood as the process of life activity.

Canadian philosopher and futurologist M.McLuen argues that the philosophy of history is based on information determinism. Depending on the way people communicate, he identified three periods in human history:

□ The first period is the period of tribal identity or "listening person". The connection of this person was limited to oral speech, the period itself lasted a very long time – from the time of Adam, to the 15th century.

□ The second period is the period of the typographic person or "seeing person". This person communicated with other people using printed text. This period lasted from the 15th century, when the Gutenberg publishing house was invented, until the 80s of the 20th century.

□ The third period is the period of information identity. A person who "sees and listens" at the same time. Such a person can be reasonably called a person of the information society. Indeed, the existence of a virtual being is associated with the human being. Because a person's thoughts, fantasies and life experiences are borderless, and he strives towards virtuality.

In this process, Man and his nature, physical being, have an important place. The presence of a Virtual entity, in turn, is associated with information technology, information technology and the communication system. Man is the founder of virtuality. Virtual reality then switches to a form of being that can exist, which affects the human mind. In our opinion, the most widespread promoter of such an effect is the internet network. This is evidenced by the fact that today the number of internet users in our country exceeds 27.2 million, the number of mobile internet users of them is 25.3 million people, 95 percent of the population of the Republic is covered by mobile internet, 54 percent of households are provided with high-speed internet access.

Research Methodology This concept has not yet been sufficiently clarified. Currently, there are several points of view regarding the essence of this concept. In culture, the concept of virtual reality dominates as an area where there is no difference between the intelligences of "virtuality", "virtual existence", and "virtual being". Modern research in the field of Social Knowledge, philosophy, psychology shows that this phenomenon is much wider than such interpretations. The variety and sufficient inconsistency of definitions of Virtual and virtual reality requires them to be regulated and clearly defined. However, despite the diversity of research, there is no holistic presentation of the problem of virtualism within the framework of the new scientific paradigm. This situation requires an in-depth analysis of the adequacy of introducing virtualism into the modern self-developing paradigm.

Analysis and results. The constantly growing flow of information, affecting the human mind, regularly expands the boundaries of its perception. This situation is associated with the visualization of information. The imaginary memory of a computer is perceived as virtual memory, which physically does not correspond to any separately obtained memory carrier. That is, virtual memory occurs as a result of the interaction of the elements of the computer. Thus, with the help of software tools that bring virtual memory to the surface, a person will be able to use a huge amount of information, and the very core of the newest vision in understanding the essence of virtual reality is the social creativity of a person. In the current conditions, when the pace of development of science and technology is gaining momentum, this worldview is called a technocratic worldview. Virtual reality technologies provide innovative opportunities in the study of the processes of human perception of various stereotypes, their impact on behavior. But in this, a new problem arises – the problem of a virtual person.

There is no doubt that the "Homo Virtualis" - virtual man problem will become the main problem of the 21st century. Nowadays even the "virtuality gene" is found in our contemporaries. This gene is hidden in labyrinths of imaginary character. From a technical and physical point of view, virtuality is a product of postindustrial civilization and the electronic revolution of information. It should be understood as a necessary plan of an informed society. All this predetermined the growth of the need for new information technologies, its proportionally accelerated development. However, the widespread adoption and implementation of such technologies has created specific problems that humanity has not faced before and cannot ignore. According to A.Tulyayev: "The interaction of consciousness and being has again become an urgent issue in the information field. This thing is especially evident when they are stuck in the general area of information flows that express knowledge, technology and programs in themselves. In such a virtual environment, however, comes to a point where, according to the rules of ethics, it is impossible to distinguish what is "good" and what is "bad" [2].

Continuing this thought, we note that the conscious activity of a person in an artificial environment created through virtual reality technologies brings to the surface the need to synthesize not only "good" and "bad", but also "useful" and "useless". N.A.Nosov is a supporter of the existence of different being. Among the variety of realities, virtual reality has its own characteristics: creativity, relevance, interactivity and autonomy. Generation means that virtual reality is produced through the activities of another reality. The expressive virtual reality of the existence of change implies existence only now and here.

Conclusion/Recommendations. As a conclusion, supporting N.A. Nosov's opinion that "the essence and composition of a Virtual being only come to the surface with the participation of a person"□3□, we recognize that virtual reality is essentially relevant only in the presence of a person.

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